

A new method of disruptive technology identification based on technology-application evolution analysis

Zhang Xuyi¹, Chen Yunwei², Jorge Gulín-González³

¹*zhangxuyi@mail.las.ac.cn*, ²*chenyw@clas.ac.cn*

Scientometrics & Evaluation Research Center (SERC), Chengdu Library and Information Center of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Chengdu, 610041, (China)

University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, School of Economics and Management, Department of Library Information and Archives Management, Beijing, 100190, (China)

³*gulinj@uci.cu*

Centro de Estudios de Matemática Computacional (CEMC), Universidad de las Ciencias Informáticas (UCI) Carretera a San A. de los Baños, Km 2½. Torrens, La Lisa, La Habana, (Cuba)

Abstract

Disruptive technologies can dramatically change existing technological paradigms and competitive market dynamics. Then, identifying potential disruptive technologies is key for companies and governments to reverse the competitive dynamics. From the perspective of technology applications, this study proposes a method and a framework for identifying disruptive technologies with the above characteristics supported on the basic idea that a technology is considered disruptive if it is applied in an entirely new field. The specific procedure that we propose includes the following steps: (i) to divide the patent data into chronological order using the sliding time window, (ii) to extract technology topics and application topics from the patents of each period, (iii) to construct a technology-application two-mode dynamic knowledge network with technology topics and application topics as nodes, (iv) to build domain and technology disruptive strength indicators to analyze the evolution of technology application fields from both intuitive and quantitative aspects and, finally, (v) to mine technology topics with cross-domain applications as potential disruptive technologies. We also will evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed solutions through comparing authoritative reports on disruptive technologies and by expert survey method.

Introduction

The concept of "disruptive technologies" was introduced in 1995 by Christensen (Bower & Christensen, 1996). Disruptive technologies may be either a fusion of existing technologies or a breakthrough of prevailing paradigms. These could initially be in the marginal market and their performances may not be as good as the products in the mainstream market, but these technologies have new functional attributes and will replace existing ones as its functions and performance are continuously improved (Su et. al., 2021), causing a great change in the existing technology paradigm and the competitive market status quo. Disruptive technologies have new features and functions that can drive profound adjustments in economic patterns and industrial forms. They are key to innovation-driven development and international competitiveness (Sun et. al., 2019), and have become the focus of national strategic layouts such as the U.S. Army's Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) (Jia et. al., 2016), Japan's Impulsing Paradigm Change through Disruptive Technologies Program (ImPACT) (Iwamatsu, 2016), etc. Among the many studies on disruptive technologies, the identification of disruptive technologies has become one of the important research hotspots. Identifying potential disruptive technologies and exploring possible future technological innovations and industrial directions are key to achieving "overtaking" and reversing competitive dynamics (Zhang et. al., 2022). Other researches have been focused on particular aspects of the disruptive technologies. For example, Lingfei et al. (2019) has studied the impact of the team size on the creation of the disruptive technologies, and demonstrated that across smaller teams have tended to disrupt science and technology with new ideas and opportunities, whereas larger teams have tended to develop existing ones.

The existing identification methods of disruptive technologies generally include two types of subjective judgment and objective analysis. The subjective judgment method mainly relies on the wisdom of experts to assess the substitutability and disruptiveness of technologies from market applications. For instance, questionnaire survey (KPMG, 2016), contextual analysis (Carlsen et. al., 2010), technology roadmap (Kai & Dou, 2021) and model analysis such as deterministic Susceptible - Infectious - Recovered – Susceptible (SIRS) epidemic model (Cheng et. al., 2017), etc. The objective analysis method mainly uses unstructured data such as patents, papers, reports, policy texts, and market data as data sources, and analyzes technology development trends through citation analysis, social networks or topic mining to identify potential disruptive technologies. For example, Li et al. (2021) to analyze the potential of technological disruption constructed quantitative indexes such as technical fusion index, technical novelty index, etc. based on patent database. In addition, multi-source data integration is a trend in objective analysis. For example, Xu et al. (2021) combine literature, patent, and news data to measure the degree of technological disruptiveness from two perspectives: development paths and citation relationships.

Disruptive technology is "a completely new technological track based on new principles, combinations and applications of science and technology" (Liu et. al., 2019). Some of the disruptive technologies are accompanied by breakthroughs in the original application areas and they are applied in completely new (or expanding) fields; frequently these technologies occupy rapidly the mainstream market as the technology matures and its functions are improved. Scientists have analyzed the connotation and potential market of disruptive technologies from the perspective of technology utility, function and industrial change. For example, Jia et al. (2022) conducted a functional analysis of the identified technologies to find potential markets for disruptive technologies. However, a few researchers have mined potential disruptive technologies from the perspective of the proliferation and evolutionary characteristics of application domains. This study proposes a new method based on the evolution analysis of patent texts and technology application fields to identify disruptive technologies with cross-domain application features. The method fully exploits the semantic information of patents, and analyzes the process and development trend of technology evolution in combination with time-series features providing new ideas for technology foresight.

Data and methods

We focus our study on the cross-domain application characteristics of disruptive technologies. In figure 1 we show the procedure to carry out the identification and verification of disruptive technologies with cross-domain application characteristics.

Figure 1. A flowchart that shows the five stages of the proposed disruptive technology identification method.

Data

Patents contain important information such as technology, specific implementation, utility, application, patent family, legal status, etc. This study focuses on the patent technologies and their application areas. The Derwent Innovations Index (DII) comprises data from more than 50 patent offices with a comprehensive coverage. Each patent in DII is summarized with “technology focus”, and also its application fields are manually classified. This study takes the biomedical field as an example. Based on the DII database, the basic information and abstracts of patents in the mentioned field are obtained through information retrieval, and potential disruptive technologies are identified through the analysis of the abstract texts.

Chronological division of technical fields

We use the sliding time window for the chronological division of patents in the target field. The window size w is the time span of patent data collected at each period. A larger window reduces the sensitivity to the changes of the recent patent technology application themes, while a smaller window will result in little patent data collected at each period, thus leading to a larger dynamic network change and distorting the subsequent index of disruptive intensities. We set w to 1 year. Also, the step size s indicates the time span of the window sliding forward across periods, indicating how often to reconstruct the network graph. We set s to 1 month in this study to ensure real-time identification of disruptive technologies.

Extracting information in patents about technology topics and their applications

After the chronological division, the technical topics and application topics are extracted from the patents of each period. For the extraction of technical topics, the "technology focus" part of DII is used as technical text, and the technical text is pre-processed by removing non-text parts, word separation, removing deactivated words and feature processing, and then the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) topic model adjusted by term frequency–inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) weights and the K-means clustering method are respectively used to cluster the technical texts in the patent set and extract the topics. For the LDA topic model, the optimal number of technical topics is determined using perplexity or likelihood estimation, while the optimal number of topics for the K-means clustering method is determined by the Davies-Bouldin criterion or the elbow rule. Comparing the two methods, the effectiveness of the model was measured in terms of both topic breadth and topic granularity. Here topic breadth measures the coverage of the extracted valid topics in the biomedical domain and topic granularity assesses the degree of refinement of the technical topics. The models with high technical topic breadth and granularity are selected to participate in the subsequent knowledge network construction. For the application topics of patents, the process of extraction is similar to that of technical topic extraction, in which the "use" part of the patent abstract is utilized as the request text to extract the application topics.

Construction of technology-application two-mode dynamic knowledge network

According to the chronological division, we construct the technology-application two-mode knowledge network in each time window. Taking the extracted technology topics and application topics as nodes, the co-occurrence relationship between technologies and applications as edges, and unfolding in chronological order, a patent technology-application two-mode dynamic knowledge network $G_t = (T_t, A_t, E_t)$ can be constructed, where T_t denotes the set of technology topics, A_t denotes the set of application topics, and E_t is a subset of the Cartesian product of T_t and A_t , representing technology-application co-occurrence relationship.

The knowledge network contains two types of nodes: technology topic and application topic. The node size indicates the topic intensity which is characterized by the frequency or expected frequency of the technology or application topic in the patent. The evolution of the technology topic intensity can reveal the change process of the technology maturity, and the change of the application topic intensity can monitor the time-series characteristics of the application path and scale in the field. In the K-means clustering algorithm, the topic intensity is expressed as the number of patents covered by the technology or application topic. In the LDA topic model, it is characterized by the number of texts supported by the topic, which is calculated as follows (Yang et. al., 2022):

$$s_{t,k} = \frac{\sum_{d=1}^{D_t} P_{d,k}}{D_t} \quad (1)$$

where $s_{t,k}$ denotes the topic strength of the k th topic in the time period t , D_t denotes the number of patents in the time period t , and $P_{d,k}$ denotes the probability that the d th document belongs to the k th topic.

The thickness of the edge between the technology node and the application node in the knowledge network indicates the co-occurrence strength between the technology topic and the application topic, which is characterized by the co-occurrence frequency or expected frequency of the technology and the application. The co-occurrence strength between the technology topic and the application topic is used to explore the evolution of the technology in terms of breakthrough, proliferation and even occupation of the mainstream market in a certain application area. When using the K-means clustering algorithm, the co-occurrence is expressed as the number of patents matched by technology-application; when technology and application topics are extracted by the LDA method, the co-occurrence is calculated as follows:

$$c_{t,i,j} = \frac{\sum_{d=1}^{D_t} P_{d,i} Q_{d,j}}{D_t} \quad (2)$$

where $c_{t,i,j}$ denotes the co-occurrence intensity between technical topic i and application topic j in the time period t , D_t denotes the number of patents in the time period t , $P_{d,i}$ denotes the probability that the d th document belongs to the i th technical topic, and $Q_{d,j}$ denotes the probability that the d th document belongs to the j th application topic.

Analysis of the evolution of technology application fields

Based on the basic assumption that part of the disruptive technologies tends to occur in the proliferation and transfer of application markets, this study identifies potential disruptive technologies with the above characteristics by analyzing the time-series evolution of technology-application two-mode dynamic knowledge networks and focusing on the generation of new links between technologies and applications. At a macro level, we construct domain disruptive intensity indicators based on the variability of industrial applications in different domains; while at a micro level, technology disruptive intensity indicators are constructed for the degree of application evolution of each technology.

At a macro level, since the constructed patent technology-application two-mode dynamic knowledge network only contains the connection between technology nodes and application nodes, it can be considered as a dynamic bipartite graph. So, the knowledge network of period

t can be expressed as a nodal directed adjacency matrix (i.e., T-A matrix) C_t , and the element of the matrix $c_{t,i,j}$ is the co-occurrence intensity between technology topic i and application topic j . The domain disruptive strength can be characterized by the graph edit distance or the cosine similarity of the corresponding T-A matrix between two neighboring period knowledge networks.

At a micro level, the intensity of technological disruption is measured by the difference between the set of application topics corresponding to each technology. The formula for calculating the similarity between two application topics is given in equation 3, where $p(\cdot)$ denotes the word distribution of application a .

$$\text{sim}(a_t, a_{t+1}) = \frac{a_t * a_{t+1}}{\|a_t\| * \|a_{t+1}\|} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (p(w|a_t) p(w|a_{t+1}))}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (p(w|a_t))^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (p(w|a_{t+1}))^2}} \quad (3)$$

Define $A_t^i = \{a_{i,1}^t, a_{i,2}^t, \dots, a_{i,N_i^t}^t\}$ as the set of application topics of technology i in the time period t , where, $a_{i,k}^t$ is the k th application topic of technology i in the time period t and N_i^t is the number of application topics of technology i in the time period t . Define the disruptive intensity of technology i in the time period t as shown in equation 4.

$$\text{Disr}_i^t = 1 - \min_{j \in \{1,2,\dots,N_i^t\}} \max_{k \in \{1,2,\dots,N_i^{t-1}\}} \{sim(a_{i,j}^t, a_{i,k}^{t-1})\} \quad (4)$$

When the technology disruptive intensity is greater than some threshold α , the potential emerging application area of the technology i in the time period t can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Appl}_i^t = \text{argmax}_{j \in \{1,2,\dots,N_i^t\}} \left\{ 1 - \max_{k \in \{1,2,\dots,N_i^{t-1}\}} \{sim(a_{i,j}^t, a_{i,k}^{t-1})\} \right\} \quad (5)$$

Using the domain and technology disruptive intensity indicators constructed above, we visualize the evolution of technology disruptive indicators throughout the life cycle of the technology domain using the period as the horizontal axis and the disruptive intensity as the vertical axis, so as to uncover potential disruptive technologies and the application areas where the technology may be used on a large scale in the future.

Identification and accuracy assessment of disruptive technologies

By observing the evolution of technology applications in various fields in different periods and the changing characteristics of disruptive intensity, we identify technology topics that have shown or are showing great application value across fields or industries, and explore potential disruptive technologies. For each technology, the full-stage disruptive intensity is calculated, and the top k technologies with the greatest disruptive intensity are selected as potential disruptive technologies; or based on the expert survey method, a suitable threshold is set, and technologies with disruptive intensity greater than this threshold are selected as potential disruptive technologies. Finally, we implement a comparison experiment with existing disruptive technology identification methods to evaluate the accuracy of our results and the effectiveness of the proposed method by comparing authoritative disruptive technology reports and/or researching from experts.

Result

Currently, we have collected 85,985 patents in the biomedical field to explore the potential disruptive technologies in this field. Based on the preliminary technology-application two-mode network, we have identified the following potentially disruptive technologies: microbiology and probiotic technology; materials science and chemical analysis technology; organic chemistry synthesis and chemical reaction conditions; genetic engineering and protein engineering techniques (gene sequences, amino acid sequences, structures of peptides and antibodies); natural drug development technology; organic chemistry and formulation methods; Chinese herbal medicine research and preparation; gene editing, cell engineering and artificial intelligence. Take the gene editing and protein sequence analysis technology as an example (Figure 2), in phase 1 (technology 13 on the left), the technology is mainly applied to cancer therapy (application 2 on the left), cardiovascular diseases and diabetes (application 6 on the left), etc. In phase 2 (technology 4 on the right), the technology is applied to more areas and the number of application scenarios increases rapidly, such as ophthalmology, infectious diseases (application 15 on the right), metabolic diseases (application 3 on the right), etc. The preliminary experiment still has flaws, such as the coarse granularity of the technology topic. Also the selection of the threshold value of the network edge weight has a relatively large impact on the experimental results. The optimization of the topic model and the robustness of the recognition method will be continued in the future.

Figure 2. Technology-Application two-mode dynamic knowledge network to demonstrate the disruptive nature of the gene editing and protein sequence analysis technology.

Conclusion and discussion

Based on the cross-domain application characteristics of some disruptive technologies, this study constructs dynamic knowledge networks and analyzes the evolution of the application areas of the technologies over time to identify potential disruptive technologies. The method can be applied in broad technology fields to technologies with the characteristic that the technology's disruptive potential, when tapped, will be used in one or more new scenarios for breakthrough applications, such as Artificial Intelligence in healthcare, blockchain in supply chain management, gene editing in agriculture, etc. On the other hand, the choice of patent database should be determined by the target technology field, taking into account the completeness and availability of data. For instance, in the biomedical field, patent databases such as Incopat, SIPO, Patentics, etc. can be selected. Also, improvements will be made in the following aspects. First, we use only patent data to discover potentially disruptive technologies. In the future, we can analyze the breakthrough applications and potential disruptions of

technologies through multiple sources of data, such as academic papers, conference papers, technical reports, industry reports, news media, etc. Second, besides focusing on the new application areas of the technology, we should also pay attention to the maturity and growth of the technology in the existing application areas, so as to assess its disruptive potential in the field. Third, with the development of S&T innovation, not only the application area of a certain technology will change, but also the technology itself will undergo changes like technological convergence, crossover and derivation, so that there is a slight difference in the word distribution of the same technical topic across phases. We will follow the laws of technology development, and pay attention to the evolution of technology topics, and construct reasonable indicators to reveal the new opportunities brought by changes in technology convergence and crossover to industrial value-added.

Acknowledge

JGG thanks for the funding provided by the Chinese Academy of Sciences President's International Fellowship Initiative (Grant No. 2021VTA0010).

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